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Commercialization of the Steel Cell[®] technology: Latest Update

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Abstract

Ceres continues to acquire commercial partners for its low-temperature metal supported SOFC technology (the 'Steel Cell[®]') based predominantly around the use of ceria. This unique design architecture allows for a robust, low cost, subsidy free fuel cell product, whilst retaining the advantages of fuel flexibility, high efficiency and low degradation.

Over the last year, several significant technological and commercial developments have taken place. The latest version 5 iteration of the core SteelCell[®] technology has completed verification and has been released to customers. This technology iteration offers higher power, the ability to operate at higher fuel utilization/efficiency and state-of-the-art performance degradation rates, whilst retaining the outstanding robustness to thermal cycling, vibration and REDOX cycling characteristic of SteelCell technology.

Major commercial developments include the commercial launch of a 4.2kW_e light commercial CHP system with Miura in Japan, and ongoing strategic collaboration agreements with both Robert Bosch in Germany, primarily for manufacturing, and Weichai Power in China, for on-vehicle applications. In addition, a new collaboration and license agreement has been signed with Doosan in South Korea to jointly develop 5-20kW_e low-carbon power generation systems.

Ceres now has active commercial programs at 1kW_e, 5kW_e, 10kW_e and 10's of kW_e and for that reason Ceres has developed an innovative 5kW_e class stack design which can be used in an array to achieve higher power outputs. Development programs are ongoing with OEM's with global reach based in Japan, North America and Europe.

To meet the rapidly increasing demand for cells for customer programs, Ceres has invested in a larger manufacturing site near Redhill, UK capable of manufacturing >2MW/y initially with space for significant expansion. Despite the considerable challenges caused by the coronavirus pandemic, production has been rapidly ramped up at the new Redhill site during 2020 with investment released for further expansion of production capacity in the UK. Significantly, our first manufacturing licensee has successfully commenced pilot production in Bamberg, Germany, under ISO9001.

Product Development of a 1kW μ CHP Hydrogen-only System Reference Design has demonstrated a 40% system level cost reduction compared to NG systems at 1kW scale at equivalent efficiency.

A further development has been the evaluation of SteelCell[®] technology for steam electrolysis applications, promising initial results of which are reported in this paper.

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Introduction

Ceres Power's unique low temperature metal-supported SteelCell® technology has now been successfully commercialized at a small scale, with a 4.2kW_e system manufactured by Miura and using Ceres stacks and system architecture being commercially available and deployed to multiple sites in Japan. This unique design architecture allows for a robust, low cost, subsidy free fuel cell product, whilst retaining the advantages of fuel flexibility, high efficiency and low degradation. Ongoing relationships with strategic partners aim towards a much larger-scale commercial deployment of the technology into multiple applications.

The current V5 generation of SteelCell® technology has been available for use by customers for over two years, and has been incorporated into multiple customer products. Operation of V5 technology at high efficiency and very low performance degradation has been demonstrated for >27kh with multiple tests ongoing. As described elsewhere in these proceedings, degradation mechanisms in SteelCell technology are well understood, with the ability to make through-life performance predictions using a combination of extensive experimental testing and mathematical modelling.

To meet demand for cells and stacks from commercial programs, Ceres has established a dedicated manufacturing site in Redhill, UK approximately 20km from the company HQ Horsham. This is now operational for the production of cells and 5kW_e stacks for both internal development and customer projects despite the challenges posed by the 2020 pandemic, and is designed to have an ultimate production capacity of >10MW/y.

Ceres currently has seen significant progress in four major strategic partners, in the public domain:

- Robert Bosch in Germany has a manufacturing license for the manufacture of both V5 cells and 5kW_e-stacks, and has set up a plant in Germany for initial low-volume production, mirroring Ceres' plant in the UK. The stacks are used in Bosch's 10kW_e power generation system, designed to operate on both natural gas and hydrogen, a number of which are currently in operation.
- Weichai Power in China is developing a 30kW_e range extender for light commercial EVs fueled on compressed natural gas using Ceres 5kW_e stacks, and Ceres engineering expertise in the design of the system and control electronics. A prototype SOFC-powered bus has been demonstrated, the first time an SOFC stack has ever been used in this series hybrid configuration in a commercial road vehicle. Development of a production-ready version of the range-extender system is ongoing.
- Doosan in South Korea signed a joint development agreement with Ceres Power in 2019 for the development of 5-20kW_e power systems for commercial applications. Doosan has very ambitious targets for the deployment of fuel cell technology in Korea, with 15GW_e targeted by 2040.
- Miura in Japan has licensed Ceres' system design for use in natural-gas fueled CHP systems in commercial buildings, using Ceres-manufactured stacks and a licensed system architecture. These 4.2kW_e systems are now commercially available on a limited basis and have been deployed successfully in Japan since October 2019. Miura is establishing a specialist maintenance team to support a wider deployment in the Japanese market.

In addition to these commercial developments, Ceres has further strategically important joint product development programs with Honda in Japan, Cummins in the USA and several other confidential relationships with major global OEMs.

As Ceres is increasingly evaluating the use of SteelCell technology for as part of the hydrogen economy. A project is underway to evaluate the use of SteelCell technology for steam electrolysis as described in the next section. This represents an additional and growing commercialization opportunity. In addition, a 1kW_e-class μ CHP system has been demonstrated fueled by pure hydrogen, with a very simple low-cost system configuration.

The hydrogen fueled μ CHP system was based on Ceres' well-established natural-gas fueled 'SteelGen' compact μ CHP demonstrator. Without the requirement for the relatively complex fuel processing system in the NG-fueled system, it was estimated the overall system cost could be reduced by ~40%. On initial testing >50% net AC electrical efficiency has been demonstrated operating on hydrogen, with opportunities to increase this to 53% or greater with better optimization of components.

1. Application of SteelCell® Technology to Hydrogen Production by Steam Electrolysis

There has been increasing interest in recent years on the application of SOC technology for electrolysis for the production of hydrogen from renewable electricity. This has been identified as an additional commercial opportunity for Ceres, not least as the potential partners interested in electrolysis are different from the partners interested in power generation. Until very recently the performance of Ceres cells/stacks in electrolysis mode has not been evaluated in detail. In principle, the use of SteelCell technology for electrolysis should retain the advantages which have already seen it chosen as the preferred SOC technology for power generation by multiple global OEMs, in particular

- Robustness to thermal cycling and unplanned system shut-downs.
- Low cost cells and stacks, and reduced system and system integration costs due to the low operating temperature.
- Retention of the thermodynamic advantages of steam electrolysis relative to low temperature water electrolysis in terms of lower specific electrical energy demand, provided a source of waste/renewable heat for steam generation is available

An additional thermodynamic advantage of SteelCell technology is the low (by SOC standards) operating temperature. This means integration of electrolyzers with external sources of waste heat to provide some of the energy for reaction (where the stack is being operated at below the thermoneutral voltage) is feasible for a wider range of processes, as a lower grade of waste heat is required.

Techno-economic analysis shows that the levelized cost of electrolytic hydrogen (LCOH) is dominated by energy cost for all technologies. Therefore, if Green Hydrogen does indeed become a \$2.5Tn industry as predicted by the Hydrogen Council [1], SOEC will have a significant advantage on LCOH for two reasons –

1. SOEC is substantially more efficient than low temperature approaches and, uniquely,
2. has the ability to utilize waste industrial heat. This is particularly relevant in the synthesis of more complex energy vectors like ammonia and e-Hydrocarbons which all present thermal integration opportunities.

Early stage analysis indicates that both #1 and #2 are true for CERES SteelCell based SOEC technology. If this is true, we believe SteelCell will be compelling in this space for similar reasons to its success in Power Generation. These attributes offers a significant advantage as most techno-economic modelling for hard-to-abate industrial sectors (ammonia synthesis, steel, concrete, synthetic hydrocarbon fuels etc.), forecasts electrical efficiency as the key driver in achieving the lowest levelized cost of hydrogen. Such models suggest an advantage for CERES LT-SOEC technology which can run at optimum operating points well below the thermo-neutral voltage whilst utilising much more abundant, lower grade heat.

Figure 1: Reversible IV curve measured on a 1cm² button cell on a 50:50 H₂/H₂O mixture at 600°C

Figure 1 shows the IV curve from a button-cell test of a SteelCell operated reversibly between -600mAcm⁻² and 600mAcm⁻². Note that Ceres makes button cells from sections cut from full-size cells, and therefore the intrinsic electrochemical performance has been validated to be fully representative. The IV curve is essentially fully reversible apart from some slight deviation from linearity at <-500mAcm⁻² which indicates fuel-side mass transport is slightly more limiting in electrolysis mode but only at current densities significantly beyond those identified as commercially relevant.

A full stack validation programme is now underway. The results show that the area specific resistance (ASR) of repeating stack units is similar in SOEC mode compared to SOFC and that ASR is relatively independent on current density within the operating space explored so far. This is in line with observations for SteelCell stacks tested in SOFC mode.

Faradaic efficiency has been determined by measuring hydrogen output using a gas flow meter as well as measuring water condensate flows downstream a condensation/separation heat exchanger. The results showed that Faradaic efficiency of SteelCell stacks is 98±0.7%. This indicates that parasitic losses due to the electronic conductivity of the CGO electrolyte are adequately suppressed and have a negligible effect on electrolysis efficiency.

A number of stacks are undergoing degradation testing at a range of commercially relevant current densities. These tests support evaluation of both microstructural evolution and degradation measurement. The ASR degradation rates for durability stacks, averaged over their respective test periods, are all in the range of $15\text{-}25\pm 5 \text{ mc}\Omega\text{cm}^2\text{kh}^{-1}$. This is in line with what is typically measured in fuel cell mode during the first few thousand hours. No clear correlation with respect to current density has been observed. The degradation rates appear to decelerate with time, a trend that is typically observed when operating SteelCell stacks in fuel cells mode due to parabolic increases in ohmic resistance, as reported elsewhere in these proceedings.

Post-test analysis using scanning electron microscopy has found no evidence of either nickel migration away from the cathode/electrolyte interface or anode delamination, both of which are widely reported as major SOEC degradation mechanisms in literature.

Therefore, the conclusion so far is that no new, SOEC specific, steady state degradation mechanism appears to present itself within the first several thousands of hours testing. Understanding of degradation is built upon extensive testing and validation of SteelCell technology in SOFC mode, which gives greater confidence in the ability to extrapolate the results of relatively short-duration SOEC tests.

Considerably more extensive testing is required at larger scales, and possible optimisation of the cell and stack design for electrolysis (current evaluation has been performed on unmodified SOFC stacks), but the initial results shown here have demonstrated proof-of-concept for the use of SteelCell technology for electrolysis.

2. Long-term Testing of Technology Validation Stacks

Figure 2 shows the population of technology validation stacks where testing started at or before the time V5 SteelCell technology was released, meaning the longest running stacks have now been operating continuously for more than 3 years. These stacks are operating under long-term steady-state durability testing to establish lifetime and the long-term performance degradation rate. All the stacks previously reported [2] are still operating with no in-service failures in the last year. The tests have all been undertaken on the 1kW_e platform, on a mixture of 150W-class stacks run with heavy instrumentation in a laboratory environment, 1kW_e -class stacks operating in stack test stands and 1kW_e -class stacks operating in full natural gas fueled micro-CHP systems. Some of the longer running 1kW_e stacks have run in both stack test stands and micro-CHP systems which explains the jumps in operating voltage, primarily due to changes in the thermal environment between the two platforms (for example the bottom of the stack tends to be hotter in a micro-CHP system than in a test stand due to heat transfer from other BOP components). An important point to note is that there is little difference in performance or degradation between the different testing environments, demonstrating that the laboratory tests are representative of real world operation. Data also exist for long-term testing of 5kW_e stacks but this is a newer stack platform so the test durations are shorter, and most 5kW_e stacks are being tested under customer programs and are thus confidential.

The stacks shown in Figure 2 are all operating at a current density of 133 mAcm^{-2} at 75% fuel utilization and 51% internal steam methane reforming, at a nominal temperature of 610°C . At the time of writing the longest running test has been running since March 2017 and has accumulated 27kh under load. All stacks are achieving long-term degradation rates of 0.2%/kh or less, which is state-of-the-art for SOFC technology. Many of the long

running stacks are showing degradation rates approaching $\sim 0.1\%/kh$ as they demonstrate burn-in behavior typical of many SOFC stacks before the degradation rates stabilize. The burn-in period before stacks approach a linear degradation rate for the SteelCell is around 8-10kh.

Several external factors affect the stack degradation rate, so these data should be considered a representative of a "Well engineered" system.

Figure 2. Mean cell voltage as a function of time for version 5 technology validation stacks under galvanostatic operation. Grid lines represent 0.2% degradation/kh.

Technology validation stacks have also been used to evaluate extending the operating window of the technology to significantly higher power densities.

Figure 3. Mean cell voltage as a function of time for V5 technology validation stack operating at 255mAcm^{-2} at 75 and 80% fuel utilization.

Figure 3 shows the results from one nominally 150W-class stack operating at a slightly higher temperature (625°C) as part of a study into the effect of temperature on performance and degradation, and 255mAcm^{-2} , meaning the stack is generating $\sim 300\text{W}$. The stack was operated on simulated reformat at 75% fuel utilization (51% internal methane reforming) for the first 8kh, and then the fuel utilization was increased to 80% without affecting the voltage degradation rate (currently averaging $-0.12\%/kh$). The stack has operated for 14.1kh and is still operating at the time of writing.

This shows the potential for operating SteelCell stacks at higher current densities in future, allowing a significant further reduction in the already highly competitive stack cost, without compromising efficiency as the lower stack operating voltage can be compensated for by operating at higher fuel utilization.

1. Conclusions

Ceres has now successfully commercialized its unique SteelCell® technology with Miura in Japan, with a commercially-available 4.2kW_e CHP system, commenced manufacturing under license in Germany and achieved a world first in the application of SOFC to commercial vehicles in China and opened new areas to exploit its technology through electrolysis. Along side these engineering successes, Ceres has established multimillion pound strategic collaboration with Robert Bosch, Weichai Power and Doosan to deploy Ceres technology at scale in their products, along with ongoing relationships with multiple other customers.

In a world-first, SteelCell stacks have been successfully deployed as the prime-mover for an electric bus by Weichai Power in China, the first time SOFC technology has ever been used for this application, reflecting the exceptional robustness of the metal-supported technology to mechanical shock and thermal cycling.

Ceres has started evaluating the application of SteelCell technology to steam electrolysis, which has demonstrated that the cells are essentially reversible, and that there are no SOEC-specific degradation mechanisms which have been identified to date. In addition,

technoeconomic analysis has shown that SteelCell stacks operating at relatively low voltages, well below the thermoneutral potential, have the potential to offer an exceptionally low normalized cost of hydrogen, as the low stack operating temperature facilitates integration with a wide range of waste/renewable heat sources by comparison with more conventional SOC technology.

The latest version 5 release of SteelCell technology continues to display very low performance degradation rates, exceptional thermal cycle tolerance and very high efficiency. This technology has been integrated into both 1kW_e and 5kW_e stack platforms for multiple applications from 1kW_e to 10s of kW_e. This world class technology continues to improve and mature and attract more and more customers for commercialization in multiple markets globally.

With these successes, Ceres validates the commercial value of its collaborative business model through the ability to scale SOFC deployment, with all the attendant benefits, significantly faster than through traditionally vertically integrated Product Development approaches. This has been achieved by rigorous R&D and Engineering. Ceres has a core corporate value of “Creative Collaboration” and continues to seek new partners to broaden the deployment of this important technology class.

References

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